

Pest management and control DISEASES

Gall dwarf – a new rice virus disease in Thailand

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In August 1979, a number of rice insects and a few severely stunted and dark-green rice plants resembling those infected with rice dwarf virus disease were collected from Uthai Thani province, 250 km north of Bangkok, Thailand. An experiment on the transmission of the disease, its symptoms on host plants, and observations by electron microscope were conducted at the Rice Pathology Branch, Bangkhen, Bangkok. The results follow:

1. Symptoms of the diseased plants resembled those of rice ragged stunt.

1. Healthy plant (left) and stunted plant (right) infected with the rice gall dwarf disease.

2. Galls appeared on gall dwarf infected plant.

3. Gall or vein swelling magnified 125 + 40.

The plants were stunted and twisted, with short dark green leaves (photo 1). Vein-swellings were round, like galls, and appeared on the outer surface of the leaf blades and sheaths (photos 2, 3). The number of galls increased as the symptoms developed. The diseased plants exhibited reduced tillering and produced few panicles.

2. Spherical virus particles were found in the dip preparation from galls of the diseased plants.

3. The zigzag-wing rice leafhopper *Recilia dorsalis* and the rice green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus* were able to transmit the disease in a persistent manner (Table 1, 2). The incubation periods were about 9–25 days in both vector species and 12–25 days in the rice plants.

This new rice virus disease found in Thailand was named *gall dwarf*. ■

Table 1. Insect transmission tests of gall dwarf isolate from insect. Thailand.

Natural insects collected from Uthai Thani, Thailand by H. Inoue in August 1979	Inoculated to healthy plants (infection) ^a	Symptom	Back Transmission	Transmission tested by	Infection ^a	Symptom
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	2 of 8	Gall dwarf		<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> <i>Recilia dorsalis</i> <i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	0 of 32 3 of 67 1 of 7	– Gall dwarf Gall dwarf

Result of serial daily transmission by a single insect.^b

Insect	Insect no.	Result at given no. of transfers																			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	2	○	○	○	W	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
	41	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
	67	○	○	W	⊙	○	W	○	●	●	●	●	○	D							
Acquisition feeding for 2 days and inoculation feeding for 1 day. Total insects used = 67																					
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	4	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	W	○	●	W	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	E
	Acquisition feeding for 1 day and inoculation feeding for 1 day. Total insects used = 7																				

^aNumber of plants showing infection with positive results and total no. of plants tested.

^b● transmitted the disease.

○ failed to transmit.

W seedling wilted.

D insect died.

● insect molted and transmitted the disease.

⊙ insect molted but failed to transmit the disease.

E insect escaped.

Table 2. Insect transmission tests of gall dwarf isolate from the plant. Thailand.

Severely stunted and dark-green rice plants resembling those with rice dwarf virus disease collected from Uthai Thani, Thailand, by T. Omura in August 1979	Transmission tested by	Infection ^a	Symptom	Back Transmission	Transmission tested by	Infection	Symptom
	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	3 of 43	Rice ragged stunt virus		<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0 of 41	–
	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	1 of 44	Gall dwarf	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	5 of 40	Gall dwarf	
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	0 of 47	–	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	0 of 53	–		

Result of back-transmission by single insect, *Recilia dorsalis*.

Insect no.	Result ^b at given no. of transfers				
	1	2	3	4	5
10	○	○	●	○	D
13	○	W	○	○	●
29	○	○	○	●	D
32	○	○	●	○	○
38	○	●	●	●	●

^a Number of plants showing infection with positive results and total no. of plants tested.

^b Acquisition feeding for 1 day, inoculation period for 7 days and inoculation feeding for 2 days (1 insect/plant). Total insects used = 40. For explanation of symbols, see footnote to Table 1.

Observations on rice gall dwarf, a new virus disease

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Galls found on the leaves and leaf sheaths of dark-green, dwarf rice plants in fields at Uthai Thani, Thailand, in August 1979 were presumed to be of a new virus disease that was named rice gall dwarf.

Leafhoppers *Nephotettix nigropictus* at early instars were used in a transmission test. After 1 day of acquisition feeding the insects were serially transferred to rice test seedlings 2 times/week. The insects transmitted rice gall dwarf in a persistent manner; of the 16 tested,

4 transmitted the disease. The minimum latent period of the virus in the insects was 14 days; the maximum, 20 days.

Seedling inoculation at the first- to third-leaf stages showed the following symptoms: dwarfing, appearance of galls along the leaf blades and sheaths, dark-green discoloration, twisting of the leaf tips, reduction in number of tillers, and death of the entire plant at later infection stages. Dwarfing and discoloration are the characteristic symptoms of the